

Evolving Professional Roles in Data Science across Industries and Academic Research

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Overview

The terms "data science" and "data analysis," though originally coined in the 1960s (Tukey, 1962), was popularised in private industry in the early 2000s as companies sought to capitalise on "big data"—the vast and complex datasets generated across various domains (Kitchin and McArdle, 2016). This was supercharged by the unparalleled data sharing in fields, from genome sequencing technology to powerful space telescopes, and information management capabilities enabled by the World Wide Web and the Internet. The demand for data-driven technology and innovation also led to the emergence and evolution of various professional roles.

This short publication traces the development of data science roles in industry and the subsequent adaptation of similar or customised roles in academia. Supported by peer-reviewed articles and online publications, we provide an overview of industry-specific roles in Table 1. In Table 2, we highlight how academic institutions have responded to the growing demand for data-driven and AI technologies in research through professionalisation of specialist data science roles.

Figure 1: Research Technical Professionals in data-led and interdisciplinary research.

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Data Science Roles in Data-Driven Industries

Recognition of the importance of data science in industry (Conway, 2013; Davenport and Patil, 2012) along with roles like Data Wranglers and Data Stewards with professional career paths and competitive compensation, was a direct response to the evolving challenges and technical requirements faced by teams across data-driven industries. In the years that followed, as data science and Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches became more widely adopted, additional specialist roles were professionalised in the commercial sector, as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Recognised Data Science Roles in Industry

This table has been organised according to the chronological emergence of professional roles as outlined in the primary or secondary publications referenced in the last column.

Data science roles	Key Responsibilities	Leadership and areas of expertise	Selected publications
Product Managers	Define strategy, roadmap, and adoption of a company's product, such as software, or specific features for an existing product based on customer and market needs. <i>First mentioned in a memo by Neil McElroy from 1931.</i>	Product and services (market adoption)	(Duke, 2018; Jílková, 2019)
UX Designers	Develop accessible, easy to use, user-centred designs that enhance the overall experience of users and/or customers to interact with products and services. <i>First UX designer roles was described for Walt Disney in 1966.</i>	Product and services (usability)	(Dickerson, 2013; Nielsen, 2017)
Data Wrangler or Data Engineers	Take unrefined sources of data and build systems for collecting, storing, and analysing data to provide research-ready datasets. They might be involved in building databases and supporting Data Scientists in carrying out data analysis.	Data toolkits	(Reeves et al., 1998; Goldston, 2008)
Developer and User Community Advocates	Engage with developers and the broader user community respectively through relevant community activities and resources, cultivate relationships, offer support, and gather feedback	Technology and community	(Mambrey et al., 1998)

Data science roles	Key Responsibilities	Leadership and areas of expertise	Selected publications
	to advocate for developer/user needs and interests within the company. These are also known as Developer Relations Advocates or Evangelists.		
Open Source Program Officers / Managers	Offer expert consultation, support and training on the effective use, adoption and development of open source software, open data, models and strategy in an organisation. These roles often work as part of Open Source Program Office (OSPO).	Open source and open working	(Rohde and Toft, 1999; Ruff, 2022)
Data Stewards	Ensure that data assets are managed, shared and used accurately and securely while following the organisation's data governance, standards and policies consistently.	Data lifecycle and data management	(IGGI, 2000)
Systems Engineers	Ensure organisational access to the most appropriate equipment and technology for their work, such as secure computing and data storage.	Infrastructure service	(IEEE, 2000)
Data Scientists	Organise and analyse data from a range of sources to gain insights, build solutions and communicate them to the wider community. They are generalists with a range of data skills who collaborate with different teams to build reusable tools.	Data and visualisation toolkits	(National Science Foundation and National Science Board, 2005)
Machine Learning (ML) Engineers	Develop and deploy machine learning models in practical applications. They work closely with Data Scientists and Research Software Engineers.	Algorithm and ML models	(Zhang and Tsai, 2005)
AI Safety Engineers	Develop methods and practices for mitigating potential risks associated with AI technologies, minimising the chances of unintended harm and enhancing the overall safety and benefits of AI systems.	AI design and machine ethics	(Yampolskiy, 2013)

Emergence of Data Science Roles in Research Settings

The professional evolutions of data science roles as seen in the private sectors are also being experienced in research across public sector and academia, leading to enhanced investment in digital up-skilling and reskilling of the workforce. Specific recognition of socio-technical aspects of data science and AI in academic research have led to professionalisation of specialist roles in some research organisations, particularly in the Global North countries.

Roles such as Data Wranglers (Goldston D, 2008) and Data Stewards (Newbold et al., 2024; Peng, 2018; Wendelborn et al., 2023) have been drawn directly from commercial enterprises. These types of professionals, recently termed Research Technical Professionals (RTPs), have received significant investment in the European countries, USA and Australia (Barker and Katz, 2022; UKRI & EPSRC, 2024; UKRI STP, 2024).

We list these RTPs with other recognised research infrastructure roles in **Table 1**. Although professionalisation of each of these roles are in different timelines across different countries and domains, their relevance in interdisciplinary data science and AI projects have been recognised by researchers worldwide. RTPs like Research Software Engineers (Baxter et al, 2012) and Research Community Managers (RCM), along with other open science promoting roles can be seen as the adoption of developer and user community advocates and Open Source Program Office (OSPO) equivalent roles from industry into academic research. We also include relatively new roles of Research Application Managers (product manager equivalent), Research Infrastructure Engineers and AI ethicists as RTPs. Professionalisation of these roles will allow academic research institutions to readily respond to emerging challenges and opportunities in data science and AI.

We also list specialists such as librarians, project managers, policy analysts, citizen science practitioners, public engagement practitioners and impact officers. These roles, although not new in academia, should be recognised as important contributors to interdisciplinary research and team science.

When tracing the emergence of the roles, it's evident that some areas of expertise have been identified several years before the professionalisation efforts begin. Unlike traditional academic roles, several of these roles are still in the early stages of professionalisation within academia. Consequently, there is a dearth of peer-reviewed literature or references to describe the skills, practices and career paths for each of these roles within research infrastructure.

Table 2: Emerging Data Science Roles in Academia

*This table has **NOT** been organised according to the chronological emergence of professional roles. We have used the most representative job titles in the first column, while acknowledging that different organisations and countries may use alternative titles to describe the same roles.*

Research Technical Professionals and Infrastructure roles	Key Responsibilities	Leadership and areas of expertise	Selected publications
Research Software Engineers (RSEs)	Develop software for academic research projects. They will typically be involved in designing and maintaining complex codebases that underpin applications of research.	Software, algorithm and infrastructure	(Hettrick, 2018; Katz and Hettrick, 2023; Sims, 2021; SocRSE, 2024)
Research Community Managers (RCMs)	Foster a collaborative environment where a diverse research community can access the socio-technical infrastructure and participatory processes they need to actively engage, get recognition and build shared agency over their work.	Inclusive and collaborative research community	(Lesser and Prusak, 2000; Leonelli and Ankeny, 2015; Wenger, 2000)
Data Wrangler or Data Engineers	Take unrefined sources of data and build systems for collecting, storing, and analysing data to provide research-ready datasets. They might be involved in building databases and supporting Data Scientists in carrying out data analysis.	Data toolkits	(Endel and Piringner, 2015; Goldston, 2008)
Data Stewards	Ensure that data assets are managed, shared and used accurately and securely while following the organisation's data governance, standards and policies consistently. Often follow best practices in open and FAIR data management and stewardship.	Data lifecycle and data management	(Newbold et al., 2024; Peng, 2018)
Open Science Managers/Leads (equivalent of OSPO team)	Develop, maintain and deliver resources and activities to inform and support researchers in the implementation of open source and open science practices. They ensure that teams follow policies, procedures, and recommendations to implement open practices in their projects.	Shaping and leading open science initiatives	(Rafols et al., 2024; Thibault et al., 2023; Winker et al., 2023)
Research Librarians	Provide researchers, academic staff and students with access to	Knowledge access and	(Faniel and Connaway,

Research Technical Professionals and Infrastructure roles	Key Responsibilities	Leadership and areas of expertise	Selected publications
	existing publications and the knowledge base needed to make their research effective. They also support them in sharing research outputs in repositories accessible to others.	sharing	2018; Ducas et al., 2020)
Research Ethicists	Help navigate ethical and societal considerations related to research and technology, ensuring that research is carried out responsibly and considers its impact on society.	Ethical considerations in the research	(Hand, 2018; Rismani and Moon, 2022)
Research Product/ Application Managers	Facilitate the adoption of research outputs by external stakeholders across domains. They work with research teams to consider the real-world applicability of the research outputs.	Translating research findings into successful products	(Jílková, 2019; R A M, 2023)
Research Computing/ Infrastructure Engineers	Ensure that researchers in an academic research organisation have access to the most appropriate equipment and technology for their work, such as secure computing and data storage.	Infrastructure service	(Chaudhry et al., 2022; Sochat, 2024)
Research Project Managers	Ensure that the research projects are executed on time while meeting the project milestones and funding requirements. They support research teams in following standards in line with the Institute's policies.	Project management	(Brocke and Lippe, 2015; Urton and Murray, 2021)
Citizen Science Practitioners or Coordinators	Engage members of the public in doing research with professional researchers/scientists. They bring a diverse set of practices ranging from crowdsourcing, to research co-creation and co-leadership.	Citizen involvement in research	(Van Vliet and Moore, 2016; von Gönner et al., 2023; Hano et al., 2020)
Public Engagement Practitioners	Develop and deliver public engagement activities to foster researcher-public engagement (and patients in health research)	Methods of public engagement	(Van Vliet and Moore, 2016; Grand et al., 2015)

Research Technical Professionals and Infrastructure roles	Key Responsibilities	Leadership and areas of expertise	Selected publications
	and vice versa, creating opportunities for knowledge exchange and involvement.		
Policy Advisors	Carry out research, provide consultations and advise researchers on regulatory and policy issues. They work with decision-makers to develop and shape policy in line with government principles.	Informs evidence-based policy decisions	(Hopkins et al., 2021; McGuire and Perna, 2023)
Research Impact Officers	Guide and support researchers to maximise the impact of research outputs and their outcomes. They develop frameworks to both plan the impact as well as assess them at different stages of research.	Maximising the real-world benefits	(Jensen et al., 2022)
AI Ethicists	Specialise in the ethical implications of AI development and application, ensuring that AI technologies are developed and used responsibly, considering potential societal impacts, and encompassing fairness, transparency, and accountability.	Responsible and beneficial development of AI	(Sanderson et al., 2022; Ali et al., 2023)

Note: The list of RTPs and infrastructure roles in Table 2 is not exhaustive. We note that organisations and research institutes across different domains and countries are taking different approaches for defining, scoping, and professionalising roles similar to these or more customised versions appropriate to their local contexts, resource availabilities and needs.

Historically, these professional roles were viewed as support staff or part of professional services. However, as evidenced by targeted funding and growing recognition, they are increasingly being considered essential research positions, requiring research-specific expertise, qualifications, and experience, forming an integral part of interdisciplinary research teams (Smaldone et al., 2022).

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In a separate publication, we share data science team personas developed for some of these roles with the insights gained from data science roles at The Alan Turing Institute (Karoune and Sharan, 2024). Other related work, including report, research article and policy briefing are shared separately and linked to the project page for [Professionalising traditional and infrastructure research roles in data science](#).

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Declarations of Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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